

THE INFLUENCE OF THE GENDER FACTOR ON THE FORMATION OF A COMMUNICATION IN THE FAMILY

Davlatova Khulkaroy Uktamovna

Andijan state insitute of foreing languages

Department of Theoretical Aspects of the English Language

Associate Professor (PhD)

Tel: +99897 581 66 55

email: dhulkaroy@inbox.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10153296>

Annotation: The article discusses and analyzes the views of some scholars on gender studies in linguistics. Gender studies in linguistics is one of the most controversial topics. Among the latest achievements of linguistics, gender studies, based on an anthropocentric approach to the study of language fields, occupy a special place. At the same time, the influence of the gender factor on the formation of a culture of communication in the family is highlighted.

Key words: gender, speech, communication, human personality, age, linguistic phenomena.

After the first half of the 20th century, new directions began to develop in linguistics, such as sociolinguistics, pragmatics, psycholinguistics, speech and communication theory, and researchers began to conduct a number of studies within the framework of pragmatics. Scientists began to pay attention to the influence of psychophysiological and social characteristics of people (gender, age, level of education) on language.[10]

Interest in gender studies in linguistics began to appear among scientists at the end of the 20th century, and at the same time new theories of human personality, the socio-psychological structure of human activity, and the process of formation of social phenomena by people appeared. which are considered. Particular attention is paid to the scientific study of biologically defined categories such as age, gender, and ethnicity. One of the main requirements of the new approach was to study the use of words and phrases suitable for gender studies, the manifestation of linguistic phenomena in language and communication.[9:154,161] Among the latest innovations in linguistics, gender studies, based on an anthropocentric approach to the study of linguistic fields, occupy a special place. The main concept of this study is the concept of gender, which is understood as the sum of a certain culture, the behavior of women and men in society, their culture and characteristics that determine their relationships with each other.[12]

The main goal of gender research conducted by linguists is the relationship of our social life to men and women, as well as the factors of human behavior associated with belonging to one or another gender. Even though the first mentions of the concept of gender in language date back to ancient times, this idea was introduced into modern linguistics in 1975 by G. Rubin's notes on the concept of gender after publication. As a result of the researchers' studies, according to the symbolic-semantic assumptions that existed at that time, the names of men and women depended on gender activity. More recent research on gender has been based on the idea that differences in language factors between men and women are determined by biological sex [12].

One of the prominent representatives among scientists is O. Espersen, E. Sapir, F. Thanks to Mauthner's interest and his research on the topic of language and gender, this topic has become a source of controversy and interest among linguists. The works of researchers mainly talk about the differences between male and female speech, the characteristics of female and male speech, and the possibilities of their use of words. According to scientists, women are less likely to use rude words and expressions. The speech creativity of men is higher than that of women.[5:62,70]

Kirilina divided gender studies of the second half of the twentieth century into two main groups. The first of them is the reflection of gender in language; this study examines the gender category, vocabulary, and the influence of gender on the speaker's speech, which linguistic means belong to men and women. Next comes speech, the speech behavior of men and women, and the peculiarities and style of their speech.[6:3]

The interest of Western scientists in the topic of gender has long been effectively studied both theoretically and practically. The results of successful research on gender stereotypes and the behavior of men and women are described in detail in special journals. Group of scientists (S. Basov, H. Lips, R. Asmore, F. Del Boca, I. H. Freese, K. Stoll, G. Fauconnier, S. L. Gilman, K. Do, L. Lewis) Scientific research on gender studies on a conceptual basis manifested itself in monographs in the form of stereotypes and approaches.[8:120]

A. According to the scientific research of W. Bernhardt "The speech of a bilingual child as a subject of lexicographic description (the situation of Russian-German bilingualism)", one of the fruitful studies was carried out by famous Russian scientists V.K. Kharchenko, S.N. Tseitlin, I.P. Amzarakov in the study of children's speech, and psycholinguistics N. I. Lepskaya, A. K. Markova, K. F. Sedov, A. M. Shakhnarovich, U. Quasthoff, K. Wagner, A. A. Leontiev.[4]

The mentioned scientists explained in detail that the method of raising boys and girls in the family is different from the time of infancy, parents buy them clothes and choose colors, everything necessary for the needs of the children, and they buy everything according to their gender.

As a result of observing the speech of boys and girls, our attention was drawn to some features characteristic of children. 3 girls and 4 boys live with their grandchildren in the house of Kholiskhan Aya, who lives at 49 Orizkor Street, Yakkasaray district, Tashkent. Grandmothers attach special importance to the upbringing of their grandchildren, especially their speech. Aya Kholiskhan's instructions for greeting children, saying goodbye, and communicating with adults are expressed in the speech of her grandchildren. For example: 6-year-old Khadija and 4-year-old Usman greet their father after coming home from work and ask how he is doing, but their grandmother taught them the same. 6-year-old Khadija whistled cheerfully:

- *Hello, father, do you work without getting tired?* - He and his father hugged. 4-year-old Usman is serious:

- *Hi, how are you?* - They shook hands like adults. As can be seen from the above example, the character of a boy and a girl is formed from a young age, and this is reflected in their speech and communication.

Gender differences are evident in all areas of our social life:

- *Why would a boy draw a line on his hair?*
- (during a haircut at the barber's)
- *For girls to pay attention.*[11] (from the speech of a 7-year-old boy)

To the 8-year-old girl Nigina by the presenter Ruhshona program of the "Bola Tilidan" - *What is a moustache? When the question was asked, the answer was "moustache and hair".*

The famous Swiss linguist J. According to the results of Piaget's research, "children begin to develop their characteristics of character and behavior from a very early age; this character is mainly manifested when communicating with peers, for example, when thinking about oneself. The scientist divided the mental development of children into uncontrolled and controlled periods before socialization [7:526]

- *Ўша гап – гап-а? – деб кўзимга синчиланди Кулкул Даведивич. – Бировга индаш йўқми ахир?*

- *Нима қиз болага ўхшаянманми? Ўғил боланинг гапи битта бўлади – тамом!*[1:108]

Борамизми, - деб сўради Эгамберди.

- *Албатта борамиз, - деди Каримберди, - ёлғончилик ўғил болага ярашмайди.*[2:112]

- *Эгамберди қизишиб, қизариб-бўзариб бораётган ўртоғининг биқинига тез-тез туртиб:*

- *Бос, бос! – деб турибди.*[2:214]

- *Оч деяпман.*

- *Очмайман. Ойи, Рашидни қаранг, эшикни тепяпти*

- *Қани тепганим, чақимчи, этигимни қорини қоқаяпман, - деди жаҳли чиқиб Рашид.*

Санобар она ишдан қайтса, телевизор яна бузилиб қолибди. Фарида бидиллаб ҳаммасини айтиб берди.[3:92]

- *Ойи, мана бунингизни қаранг, тилини чиқариб, мени масхара қиляпти, ўпкаси тўлиб чинакамига йиғламсираб деди Фарида.*[3:220]

From the above examples, it can be understood that the uniqueness of the speech of boys and girls in the family is manifested in the process of their communication. In the first example, the main character of the story by the beloved children's writer Anwar Obidzhon, Motivoy, reflects in his speech the upbringing of older people, especially the men in the family: **"A boy can only say one thing"**. In the second example, through the sentence taken from the speech of Egamberdi, one of the main characters of the story, "the boy does not lie", as a result of his busyness with reading many books, some phrases from the stories were transferred to his speech. In the next example, an example is taken from the speeches of two friends, Karimberdi and Egamberdi. Egamberdi lives in an intelligent family, but his mother died when he was young, and his stepmother, sister, and father live together, some words in his speech are sometimes bookish, and sometimes he uses some rude words characteristic of boys: **"Beat, beat!"** we may read. In the following example, we used the brother-sister speech as an example. 8-year-old Farida complains to her mother about her brother Rashid's rough treatment of her sister: **"Mum, look at Rashid, he's kicking the door."** Rashid (6th grade) is the only boy in the family, even though his parents created all the conditions for him to receive a good education, he does poorly at school, and from his speech it is clear that he uses lies more to get out of the situation. The last examples are taken from Farida's speech. Compared to boys, girls convey news faster, as we see from Farida's speech. **"Farida told me everything in a whisper," "she stuck out her tongue and laughed at me."**

In conclusion, it can be said that gender studies in linguistics are one of the most controversial areas among scientists. Gender studies, based on an anthropocentric approach to the study of these fields, are distinguished by occupying an important place among the latest innovations in linguistics. Above we gave some examples of the speech of children raised in different families of our social life. We will continue again in our future work.

References:

1. Анвар Обиджон Мўттивоймисан, Миттивоймисан? 108 бет Қисса. "Шарқ" нашриёти-Матбаа бош тағририяти – 2019.
2. Xudoyberdi To'xtaboyev. Quyonlar saltanati. 112-bet. Sarguzasht roman. Toshkent. "Yangi asr avlodi" 2019 yil. 253 bet
3. Xudoyberdi To'xtaboyev. Qaylardasan bolaligim. 91-bet. Qissalar, ertaklar, hikoyalar. Yangi asr avlodi. TOSHKENT. 2020. 220 bet
4. Бернгардт, О. В. Речь ребенка-билингва как предмет лексикографического описания (ситуация русско-немецкого двуязычия [Текст] : дис. ... канд. фил. наук : 10. 02. 19 / Бернгардт Оксана Вячеславов-на. – Ярославль, 2009. – 218
5. Гриценко, Е. С. Типология асимметричных отношений в гендерной категоризации [Текст] / Е. С. Гриценко // Вестник Нижегородского государственного лингвистического ун-та им. Н. А. Добролюбова. – Выпуск 1. – Н. Новгород : НГЛУ, 2005. – С. 62 – 70.
6. Кирилина, А. В., Томская, М. В. Лингвистические гендерные исследования [Текст] / А. В. Кирилина, М. В. Томская // Отечественные записки. – М. . – 2005. – № 2 (23). – С. 3.
7. Пиаже, Ж. Речь и мышление ребенка [Текст] / сост., новая ред., пер. с фр., коммент. Вал. А. Лукова, Вл. А. Лукова. – М. : Педагогика-Пресс, 1994. – 526 с.
8. Рябова, Т. Б. Стереотипы и стереотипизация как проблема гендерных исследований [Текст] / Т. Б. Рябова // Личность. Культура. Общество. – Т. V. – Вып. 1–2 (15–16). – 2003. – С. 120–139
9. Смит, С. Постмодернизм и социальная история на западе : проблемы и перспективы [Текст] / С. Смит // Вопросы истории. – 1997. – № 8. – С. 154–161
10. Skachkova, I. I. Gender na japroblematika v zarubezhnom teoreticheskom jazykoznanii: k istorii voprosa [Tekst] / I. I. Skachkova // Vestnik TGJeU, Teorija metodologijagendernyh issledovanij. – 2009. – № 4.
11. <https://elib.bsu.by/bitstream/123456789/164715/1/>
12. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XZQa8m2NjMU>
13. Davlatova, h. (2022). The influence of the family on the development of children's mind and speech. scientific journal of the fergana state university, (1), 51-51.
14. Uktamovna, h. d. (2019). Opportunities for english-speaking voices in the speech of children of the first school age. problems and solutions of advanced scientific research, 1(1), 226-229.